

Carpanthea pomeridiana Vetkousie

Decoding
South Africa's
Biodiversity

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Phylum: Tracheophyta

Estimated genome size: 1 390 million DNA base pairs (1.39 Gigabases)

Organism size: 150 – 300 millimeters in height

Distribution:

Restricted to the soft sandy coastal regions of the summer-dry Western Cape, from Langebaan to the Cape Flats, also with outliers in sandy regions near Worcester in the Breede River Valley. Always confined to open areas in full sun, in flat terrain or on dunes, in soft sand. It grows in the Strandveld Biome and especially common along the West Coast.

Importance:

A very useful edible plant formerly eaten by the Koi people, and by the colonists on the Cape Peninsula and Cape Flats. The young fleshy capsules are eaten as a lettuce or prepared in a stew. Collect the young fleshy fruits, boil and add to meat dishes. Vetkousie is also a popular garden annual, providing a show of golden flowers in spring.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 52.64 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 10.5 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Genome length: 2.43 Gigabases

BUSCO completeness score (single and duplicated genes): 98.6%

[Single: 40.2%, Duplicated: 58.4%]

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